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Planning the Future of Research & Innovation in the European University Alliance UNITE!

Data Management Plan

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Deliverable

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Abstract	<p>The Data Management Plan (DMP) of UNITE.H2020 project, required by the Open Data Research (ORD) pilot to which the project participates, describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated during the project and after the project end.</p> <p>The plan aims to provide common guidelines as suggestion for the UNITE.H2020 consortium for the management of the project</p>

research data. It gives an overview of the type and format of these data and of the storage and sharing systems also in relation to the objectives of the project and to the data utility. Moreover, in view of making data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR), the DMP includes information about the handling of research data during and after the end of the project, which methodology & standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/ made accessible and how data will be curated and preserved. The plan also considers the ORD pilot requirements for open access provision to the results associated to the peer-reviewed publications.

The first version of the UNITE.H2020 DMP, delivered within six months of the start of the project, reflects the initial plan jointly agreed by the consortium about the managing of the project research data in accordance with the FAIR data principle and EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The DMP will be updated at least in the context of the periodic evaluation of the project and if any relevant changes will occur over the course of the project.

History of changes

Version	Date	Author(s) – Partner(s)	Reviewer(s) – Partner(s)	Description
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v0.2	04 June 2021	Politecnico di Torino (POLITO)	All partners	Revised by partners
v1.0	29 June 2021	Politecnico di Torino (POLITO)		Final version to be submitted to EC

Abbreviation list

- CA – Consortium Agreement
- DOI - Digital Object Identifier
- EC – European Commission
- EEA – European Education Area
- ERA – European Research Area
- GA – Grant Agreement
- GDPR - General Data Protection Regulation
- HR – Human Resources
- ORD Pilot - Open Research Data Pilot
- PC – Project Coordinator
- R&I - Research and Innovation
- STEM – Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
- TT – Technology Transfer
- WP – Work Package

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1 Introduction

UNITE.H2020 participates to the extended Open Research Data (ORD) pilot, which aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of the research data generated by H2020 projects. The ORD pilot requires the drafting of a Data Management Plan (DMP) describing the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed, managed and shared by Horizon 2020 projects in accordance with the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) data principles.

The UNITE.H2020 Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to provide common guidelines as suggestion for the UNITE.H2020 consortium for the management of the research project data. The plan states what data will be created and how and outline the plans for sharing and preservation, noting what is appropriate, given the nature of the data and any restrictions that may need to be applied.

The DMP will be updated at least in the context of the periodic evaluation of the project at month 18 and if any significant changes occur over the course of the project.

2 Data Summary

2.1 Overview of the data in relation to the objectives of the project

2.1.1 OVERVIEW AND OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The **University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering - Unite!** - is one of the first 17 **European University Alliances** originated from the Unite! E+ project, selected in a pilot call for proposals under the Erasmus+ programme, as part of the EC initiatives for the establishment of a European Education Area (EEA) enabling all young people to benefit from the best education and training and to find employment across Europe.

Involving **7 top level European universities** (Technical University of Darmstadt – coordinator of the Unite! alliance, Aalto University, Grenoble INP graduate schools of engineering and management - University Grenoble Alpes, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Universidade de Lisboa, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech) highly ranked in their shared focus areas - Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), architecture and design, the Unite! Alliance kicked-off in early November 2019 with the **Unite! E+ project** aiming at developing a long-term joint strategy for education.

The **UNITE.H2020 project**, started on January 1st 2021, involves the seven universities of the Unite! Alliance and is coordinated by Politecnico di Torino. The project was selected in a call related to the Horizon 2020 action to support the R&I dimension of the European Universities with the aim of contributing to the ERA (European Research Area) together with the EEA.

The overall objective of UNITE.H2020 is to develop a shared, integrated, long-term R&I strategy for the Unite! European University Alliance, emphasizing its STEM nature, that structurally and sustainably impacts society addressing the SDGs and the EU Missions. Through the UNITE.H2020 project, the Unite! Alliance aims at taking up the challenge launched by the EC to develop, in synergy with its education dimension implemented by the Unite! E+ project, a **shared, integrated, long-term research and innovation (R&I) strategy through the definition of a common R&I agenda**, while developing, during the 3-year project, several **pilot initiatives** in the field of **Energy** - with special reference to **the Green Deal, Artificial Intelligence and Industry 4.0**.

2.1.2 PURPOSE AND NATURE OF THE DATA

UNITE.H2020 project activities are organized in **9 Work Packages (WPs)**.

WP1 (Project management) and WP9 (Disseminating and communicating Unite!) data are not research data and will not be object of the DMP.

WP2 coordinates the definition of the **common R&I agenda and action plan of Unite!** by collecting the inputs by the other WPs (**from WP3 to WP8**), which focus on one of the seven policy areas or **modules for institutional transformation in the R&I dimension**. The main objectives and activities of WPs from WP2 to WP8 are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Main objectives and activities of UNITE.H2020 research Work Packages

<p>WP2 - Common R&I agenda</p> <p>Development of a common Unite! R&I agenda with coordinated pilots/ case studies of the other WPs. WP2 specific pilots will be the creation of a network of R&I services (IRIS) and an open network of experts (researchers) of the partners' universities.</p>
<p>WP3 - Sharing infrastructures and resources</p> <p>Development of a guideline for sharing infrastructures among Unite! universities, offering a better view among partners on their existing RIs, sharing their good practices and initiating common research projects. Case studies of access to the shared RIs by researchers cooperating in joint research activities.</p>
<p>WP4 - Reinforcing academia-business cooperation</p> <p>Creation of a community of Technology Transfer Offices of Unite! universities to improve the co-working of academia and companies in the Unite! ecosystems. Actions to help industries to implement an SDG agenda and an open community on "Enabling Smart Green Markets" within Unite!.</p>
<p>WP5 - Strengthening human capital</p> <p>Collection and analysis of best practices and policies related to human resources' motivation, equality, career progress and reward in partner institutions to design, develop and propose common methodologies, tools and procedures for human Resources (HR) and talents</p>
<p>WP6 - Creating a High Impact European Open Science and Innovation University</p> <p>Alignment and reinforcement of partner initiatives towards a common open science and innovation institutional transformation vision by analysing about 70 research groups: (1) Best practices of open science and innovation of research teams (2) mechanism and inducers and inhibitors of open science.</p>
<p>WP7 - A Unite! strategy for societal outreach and involvement of citizens in R&I</p> <p>Definition of a strategy on how to involve societal organizations in the research and innovation activities carried out by the Unite! alliance. Tools for citizens outreach (Webinar/ Courses/ Moocs).</p>
<p>WP8 - Exploring collaboration potential and joint structures of European University Alliances</p> <p>Selection of other European University alliances/ groups of alliances that are complementary to Unite! to share good practices and tackle common barriers. Pilot collaboration areas with other European University alliances.</p>

In the first part of the project, all the WPs from WP2 to WP8 will carry out the **analysis of the state of the art of the R&I dimension** in the Unite! Universities resulting in **the definition of a common R&I Agenda**, coordinated by WP2. Then, the R&I Agenda will be implemented by means of an action plans made of **pilots/ case studies** developed within the different WPs followed by a final cost-benefit analysis and definition of **guidelines for future models and actions** of the Alliance.

All the WPs from WP2 to WP8 will follow four phases of the work plan with associated collected and generated data:

- 1) Analysis of the state of the art referred to the WP specific topic → collection of data resulting from DESK RESEARCH/ SURVEYS/ INTERVIEWS**

- WPs from WP3 to WP8: desk researches/ surveys/ interviews collecting data (e.g. from partners' university offices / researchers/ industries/ civil society) on the topic of the different WPs, that are research infrastructures (WP3), industry connections (WP4), human capital (WP5), open science (WP6), civil society connections (WP7) and other European University Alliance (WP8).
- WP2: desk research of the partners' university strategic plans, the EU, local and global policies and opportunities and the post pandemic scene to evaluate possible convergence on multidisciplinary R&I areas.

2) Elaboration of the collected data → drafting of REPORTS/ HANDBOOKS/ CATALOGUES/ REPOSITORIES in which pilot actions are proposed in each WPs

- WPs from WP3 to WP8: analysis of the data obtained by desk researches/ surveys/ interviews to study the state of the art, needs, prospective resources of Unite! partners' universities and stakeholders in the topic of the different WPs and summary of the results in reports/ handbooks/ catalogues/ repositories, also proposing actions/ pilots.
- WP2: Through the analysis of WP2 and the inputs from the other WPs, selection of the pilots/ case studies for the Unite! shared agenda and action plan, coordinated by WP2.

3) Implementation and monitoring of the proposed and approved pilot actions → collection of DATA FOR THE MONITORING/ EVALUATION OF THE PILOT ACTION

- Implementation of the pilot actions and collection of data referred to results of the pilot actions developed in the different WPs to monitor and evaluate them.

4) Elaboration of the collected data about the pilot actions → drafting of DRAFT REPORTS/ WHITE PAPERS/ GUIDELINES for the future development of the Unite! R&I Agenda

- The collected data related to the results of the different pilot studies will be used to draft reports/ white papers/ guidelines for the future development of the Unite! R&I Agenda

2.1.3 TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA

On the basis of what described in Section 2.1.2, project data will consist mainly of:

- 1) data from desk researches/ surveys/ interviews
- 2) reports/ handbooks/ catalogues/ repositories resulting from the analysis and elaboration of the desk researches/ surveys/ interviews
- 3) data referred to the results of the pilot actions implementation

- 4) Draft reports/ papers/ guidelines resulting from the analysis and elaboration of the results of the pilot actions

The project data will consist mainly – but not exclusively – of the following types and formats:

- **Text documents:** as a general rule, *Word files* (e.g. .DOCX, .RTF file extension) will be used for drafting text documents, which could be shared in this format for modification among the project participants, while *PDF files* will be used for the final version of the documents
- **Presentations:** *Power Point files* (e.g. .pptx file extension) will be commonly used to draft project slide shows, while *PDF files* will be used for the final version of the documents
- **Spreadsheets:** data could be collected and/or organized in spreadsheets, such as *Excel files* (e.g. .xlsx file extension)
- **Images/ photos and audio/ video recordings:** different file extension for images/ photos (e.g. .jpg, .png), audio (e.g. .wav, .mp3, .ogg) and video (e.g. .mp4, .avi file extension) recordings will be used.

Some of the formats may be proprietary such as excel and word or ppt, however these formats will be used for efficiency sake during the active data management and analysis steps in the project. We will check for compatibility issues, if any, with partners. We want to emphasise that for long term preservation we will only use open and preservation friendly formats such as PDF and csv.

2.1.4 PERSONAL DATA

Personal data of the project participants as well as of other people involved in the project activities such as surveys/ desk researches/ interviews/ case studies/ etc. will be treated following the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as further explained in Section 6.

2.1.5 RE-USED DATA

The following type of already existing data – but not exclusively – will be **re-used**:

- **Official documents of partner Institution:** e.g. Strategic Plans, Policies, Regulations, data related to previous and ongoing partner's Institution activities/ initiatives; useful for example for the analysis of the state of the art carried out by the WPs, as well as to plan, implement, monitor and evaluate the pilots.
- **Data of the Unite! Alliance:** e.g. data collected during the Unite! E+ project as well as Unite! Alliances templates, communication plan, official documents; useful to implement and integrate the UNITE.H2020 activities in the Unite! Alliance.
- **Official documents at the global, EU and local level:** e.g. policies at global, EU and local level, funding programmes; useful to plan, implement, monitor and evaluate the pilots.

Depending on the data to be re-used, the need for a specific access permission by a single partner or the whole consortium will be evaluated.

2.1.6 EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA

Most of the data will be text files, spreadsheets or presentations. We expect an overall data size of about 300 GB.

2.2 Data utility and storage/ sharing systems

2.2.1 STORAGE AND SHARING SYSTEMS

The data generated/ collected by the seven UNITE.H2020 partners can be:

- **Partners' research data:** all the data generated/ collected by a specific partner
- **WP's research data:** all the data generated/ collected in the context of a specific WP
- **Project research data:** all the project data that can be useful to the whole consortium and, in some cases, to the whole Unite! Alliance and/or other groups (e.g. other alliances, stakeholders)

These data will be appropriately stored and shared among partners and, for some of them, with others outside the consortium using different storage and sharing systems:

Partner's internal data storage system – for partners' research data and backup of WP data

Each project partners will use its internal facilities to store all the data generated/ collected by the UNITE.H2020 members of that partner (e.g. data collected with desk research/ interviews/ surveys and for the monitoring of the pilot activities, internal working documents). Each beneficiary should ensure adequate backup and data recovery system for its own research data stored at their local storage systems for the time period required in accordance with GA (five years after the payment and until the end of any on-going checks, reviews, audits, investigations, litigation or other pursuits of claims under the Agreement). Moreover, WP leaders are encouraged to keep a backup of all the data of the WP activities on their internal institutional storage systems for the required time period in accordance with GA. Partners are also responsible to treat personal data collected and stored at their facilities in accordance with GDPR.

Microsoft Team: PRJ-UNITE_H2020/ other systems – for WP research data/ collaborative files

A Microsoft Team of the project has been created (PRJ-UNITE_H2020) and it is available to store and share the WP data among the WP team in WP specific folders or channels, especially for the WP's collaborative working documents. However, each WP Leader can define the most suitable storing and sharing system for the WP's internal data other than Teams. Also documents needing collaborative editing from the whole consortium can be shared on the PRJ-UNITE_H2020 Team. As already mentioned, WP leaders should also keep a backup of all the data of the WP activities on their internal institutional storage systems for the required time period in accordance with GA.

uShare project repository – for project research data to be shared among the whole consortium / whole Unite! alliance

The uShare repository of the Unite! Alliance (<https://ushare.unite-university.eu/#/>) will be used to share all the relevant project data, including research data, that can be useful to the whole consortium to follow the development of the project. A uShare account is created for all the UNITE.H2020 members. In addition to the partner’s internal storage system and WP storage system, each partner and WP leader should store all the relevant data on uShare in order to share and collect all the relevant data related to the project activity in a unique repository. uShare repository is used by the whole Unite! Alliance. Depending on the data type, different type of permission (i.e. reading, writing) can be set for the uShare folders and also private folders can be created with limited access permission. Each project member has reading permission in all the project folders and writing permission in the WP in which is involved.

Zenodo – for project open research data

Zenodo repository will be used to store and share the UNITE.H2020 research data that the consortium will decide to make open. An *ad hoc* community will be created for UNITE.H2020 project data.

Joint digital platform

A joint digital platform will be developed connecting Research Offices, Technology Transfer Offices and HR staff of the Unite! Universities as well as initiatives developed in the different WPs of the 7 Unite! partners in the project. The definition of its features, contents and access policy is in progress.

Other data storing and sharing systems of the UNITE.H2020 project are the Unite! (<https://www.unite-university.eu/>) and the **partner’s websites** with pages dedicated to Unite! and associated projects, the **Alliance social media** and the **partner’s OA publications institutional repositories**. However, since they are related to communication and dissemination activities, they will not be object of the DMP.

2.2.2 DATA UTILITY

The different research data (partners’, WP’s and project research data) could be useful to a specific group of people (“data utility”). The potential data utility, storage/ sharing mode and scope are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Data utility

Data utility	Storage/ sharing scope	Storage/ sharing mode	Examples of data
Partners’ research data			
Single partner	To implement the project activities For data storage and preservation	Partner’s internal data storage system	- Data generated/ collected by the partner - Internal partner’s working documents
WP’s research data			
WP members	To implement coordination and collaboration among partners on the project activities on the transformation modules	Defined by each WP leader (e.g. Microsoft Teams: PRJ-UNITE_H2020)	- Data generated/ collected for the specific WP - Internal WP’s working documents

Project research data			
Whole project consortium	<p>For the coordination and collaboration among partners on the project activities on the transformation modules</p> <p>To follow the project activities development</p>	uShare, Teams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All the most relevant data generated/ collected in the project - Projects collaborative working documents (e.g. in Teams)
Whole Unite! Alliance	To follow the development of the R&I dimension of the Unite! Alliance and integrate the alliance activities with that of the UNITE.H2020 project	uShare	<p>Desk researches/ interviews/ surveys, data from pilot analysis, reports/ catalogues/ repositories/ white papers/ handbooks/ guidelines/ handbooks/ guidelines</p>
Other Universities/ Alliances/ Networks (e.g. EUA, CLUSTER, Magalhaes)	<p>To be informed about the state of the art about the seven transformation modules in different universities and pilots/cases studies development.</p> <p>To be informed about the Unite! Alliance and its development model</p> <p>To set the basis for collaboration with Unite! Alliance (e.g. WP8 activities)</p>	<p>Zenodo</p> <p>Other systems (case-by-case evaluation)</p>	
Researchers	<p>To be informed about the state of the art about the seven transformation modules in different universities and pilots/case studies development to be used in similar research studies</p> <p>To be informed about the transformation of the EU R&I dimension</p> <p>To be informed about the project activities that involves the R&I dimension of the universities Unite!</p>		
Students	<p>For the work related to thesis</p> <p>To be informed about the transformation of the EU R&I dimension</p> <p>To be informed about the project activities that involves the R&I dimension of the universities of Unite!</p>		
Policy makers, National and Local Governments	<p>To be informed about the transformation of the EU R&I dimension</p> <p>To be informed about the Unite! development</p> <p>To receive inputs for the implementation of specific actions (e.g. funding) regarding the future of the European University Alliances</p>	<p>Zenodo</p> <p>Other systems (case-by-case evaluation)</p>	White papers/ handbooks/ guidelines

Industry	To be informed about the Unite! development and impact To be informed and get involved in specific activities of the projects (e.g. WP4 activities)		
Civil society	To be informed about the transformation of the EU R&I dimension To be informed and get involved in specific activities of the projects (e.g. WP7 activities)		
EC	To follow the development of the Alliances and in particular of the Unite! Alliance. To receive inputs for the full roll out of the European University Alliances and the related future actions.		

3 FAIR data

H2020 beneficiaries are required to make their data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) with the aim to allow knowledge discovery and innovation and subsequent data and knowledge integration and reuse. After an overview of the metadata used in UNITE.H2020, the following sections refer to the UNITE.H2020 approach to meet these requirements.

METADATA. The presence of metadata is a common and key element for all FAIR data requirements. In UNITE.H2020 project, metadata contributing to make data FAIR will consist in all the data-related information.

For the most relevant and official documents, such as the project deliverables/ reports/ white papers, a **common template** will be used with the metadata to be included at the beginning of the document.

As an example, metadata in the project **deliverables** could be:

- Document title
- Project Title
- Project Acronym
- Grant Agreement Number
- Project Call
- Funder
- Project starting date
- Duration
- Work Package
- Deliverable

Deliverable leader
Deliverable type
Dissemination level
Deliverable due date
Deliverable submission date
Author(s) – Partner(s)
Document version and date
Keywords
Abstract
History of changes table (e.g. version, date, author(s), partner(s), description)
Table of contents
Abbreviation list and/or legend

Metadata associated to the data file (external to it). Some repositories (e.g. Zenodo) allow the insertion of metadata that will be associated to the uploaded document.

Readme files. Metadata could be also provided in specific readme files, for example to outline the content and organization of a folder, facilitating data findability, or to clarify the relation among datasets, helping data re-use.

3.1 Making data FINDABLE, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 DISCOVERABILITY OF DATA (METADATA PROVISION)

As a general rule, clear **naming and organization** of the project data in the different storing and sharing systems will be carried out to favour data discoverability.

To favour data discoverability, depending on the data and storage system, a **readme file** could be also provided, consisting in a text file in the main folder with description of the folder structure and related files.

In the following, for the different storage systems, the folder structure and metadata facilitating data findability are reported.

Discoverability in the partner's internal data storage system: the data will be organized in different folders based on the data related topic and named with a shared naming system aiming at describing the file content.

Discoverability in Microsoft Team - PRJ-UNITE_H2020: the data will be organized in different folders/channels on the basis if the data related topic. A specific folder and/or channel for each WP.

Discoverability in uShare: clear file naming and organization in different sections (i.e. Communities) corresponding to the different WPs; a readme file in the main folder could be added to outline the folder content and data organization.

Discoverability in Zenodo: creation of a community dedicated to the UNITE.H2020 project, collecting all the project related file stored on Zenodo; editing of metadata associated to the uploaded file (e.g keywords, type of document and DOI).

3.1.2 IDENTIFIABILITY OF DATA – STANDARD IDENTIFICATION MECHANISM

The open data will have an associated DOI, created in Zenodo.

Moreover, to identify documents related to the UNITE.H2020 project, the name of the project will be always indicated in the file name, as further described in the following section.

3.1.3 NAMING CONVENTION

A shared naming convention will be used for the data files. Depending of the kind of data, the file name can include different information, as reported below (in bold the parts of the name that should always be present):

```
<date:yyyy.mm.dd> UNITE.H2020 <WP  
number>_<description1>_<description2>_<person(s)/partner(s)>_<file version>_rev <revising  
partner>_<date of revision>_upd<dd.Month.yyyy>.<ext>
```

Date: date of the event to which it is referred, such as a meeting, workshop

Project name: UNITE.H2020

WP number: for data referred to a specific WP

Description1: Main topic/ event to which the file is referred

Description2 (3, 4..): further information to better describe the topic

Person(s)/Partner(s): SurnameN of author(s) or person(s)/partner(s) the file is referred to

File version: for file derived by a revision procedure (e.g. periodic revision of the Data Management Plan, revision procedure of a Deliverable by partners)

Partner(s)/person(s) revising the file

Date of revision

Date of update: for files subjected to periodic update

File extension

Examples:

UNITE.H2020_WP1_D1.1_Data Management Plan_v1.0.pdf

UNITE.H2020_<WP>_<description1>_<description2>_<file version>.<ext>

2021.01.29_UNITE.H2020_KoM_Agenda.pdf

<date:yyyy.mm.dd>_UNITE.H2020_<description1>_<description2>.<ext>

2021.01.29_UNITE.H2020_KoM_Overview of the UNITE.H2020_ZaninoR.pdf

<date:yyyy.mm.dd>_UNITE.H2020_<description1>_<description2>_<person(s)/partner(s)>.<ext>

UNITE.H2020_WP participants_upd 24Feb21.xlsx

UNITE.H2020_<description1>_upd<dd.Month.yyyy>.<ext>

UNITE.H2020_WP8_Evaluation criteria_rev POLITICO. xlsx

UNITE.H2020_<WP>_<description1>_<description12>_rev <revising partner>.<ext>

3.1.4 APPROACH TOWARDS SEARCH KEYWORDS

File names will be as descriptive as possible so that the search process based on the file name will be enough in most cases. For the most relevant and official documents (e.g. project deliverables), **keywords** will be included in the file as metadata thus facilitating data discoverability. Moreover, keywords will be indicated as metadata for the data stored on Zenodo.

3.1.5 APPROACH FOR CLEAR VERSIONING

For **documents needing the draft of different versions** (e.g. the Data Management Plan), the file version will be indicated in the file name (see section 3.1.3 above). The main author will indicate the file version of the first draft (i.e. v0.1) and then send the draft to the partner for revision. After partner's revision, the author will edit a new version of the file including all the inputs received by the partners (i.e. v0.2) and, if needed, send it again for a further revision. When the revision phase is completed, the author will edit the final version of the file (i.e. v.1.0). When a new revision is needed (e.g. Data Management Plan to be updated after some months), the author will draft the new version (i.e. v1.1) that will be revised by the partners one or more times leading to different version (i.e. v1.2, v1.3 etc.) until the final new one has reached (i.e. v2.0).

e.g. UNITE.H2020_WP1_D1.1_Data management Plan_v1.0

The person(s) revising the file could add the partner name and/or person(s) name in the file name. For these files, the revision history table will be clearly indicated as metadata in the file itself.

3.2 Making data openly ACCESSIBLE

UNITE.H2020 participates to the extended Open Research Data (ORD) pilot, which aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by H2020 projects in line with the H2020 Open Access policy.

3.2.1 OPEN AND CLOSED DATA

The project will combine different measures to foster open access to the project research data.

In accordance with the OA obligations, for dissemination purpose, in addition to peer reviewed publications, also research data needed to validate the publications will be made openly accessible. In accordance with the project Grant Agreement (GA), roadmaps, guidelines, handbooks, position and

white papers that will be developed by UNITE.H2020 will be made openly accessible only if in agreement with GA (e.g. not confidential deliverable), with timing to be defined over the course of the project.

Moreover, each WP leader could propose a set of qualitative data to be made openly available over the course of the project, which has to be approved by the whole consortium (e.g. desk researches/ surveys/ interviews/ case studies/ data collected for the pilot action evaluation), in accordance with GA.

Personal data, unless specific consent given, will be not openly accessible, unless in the form of anonymised data. All the project data that will not be considered suitable for open access by the consortium will be kept closed.

3.2.2 METHODS OR SOFTWARE TOOLS NEEDED TO ACCESS THE DATA

Most of the data will be text documents, presentations, spreadsheets, images, audio and video, not requiring specific software tools to access the data.

3.2.3 DEPOSITION AND ACCESS PROVISION

Data that has been selected for open access will be stored on Zenodo repository and made openly accessible with timing/ restriction evaluated and agreed by the whole consortium on a case-by-case basis over the course of the project.

The deposition of close data on specific repository, such as DANS (<https://dans.knaw.nl/en>), will be also evaluated.

3.3 Making data INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DATA INTEROPERABILITY

Most of the project data could be easily shared among researchers, since they will be files requiring **common software** to be read and modified. Most of the data will be text documents as *Word* or *PDF files* (e.g. .DOCX, .RTF, .pdf), presentations as *Power Point* (e.g. .pptx) or *PDF files*, spreadsheets as *Excel files* (e.g. .xlsx), images (e.g. .jpg, .png), audio (e.g. .wav, .mp3, .ogg) and video (e.g. .mp4, .avi). Data in these file formats are expected to be interoperable among the project partners. However, as reported in Section 2.1.3, other formats will also be specifically evaluated if any interoperability problem will arise among partners and also for the files that needs to be shared outside the UNITE.H2020 project (e.g. open data) in order to increase data interoperability. For example, spreadsheets could be made open available in CSV format.

3.3.2 STANDARD VOCABULARY FOR INTER-DISCIPLINARY INTEROPERABILITY

Depending on the specific topic, the standard language of the related discipline will be used in the document. In view of an inter-disciplinary interoperability, the presence of an abbreviation list could facilitate the text readability and comprehension to researchers of different areas.

3.4 Increase data RE-USE (through clarifying licences)

3.4.1 METADATA FOR DATA RE-USE

The **naming of the file** and their **clear organization in different folders**, as well as associated metadata (see also metadata description at the beginning of Section 3) will allow the understanding and contextualization of the data, facilitating data re-use.

As regards **metadata**, in all the documents, the title, date and author(s) will be indicated to allow the contextualization of the data. Moreover, for the most relevant documents (e.g. project deliverables), additional metadata will be provided in the document itself, and among them, the **summary** and the **file version** could be useful for data re-use, for example during draft revision among the project partners.

For more complex documents, all the information needed to better understand the data will be included directly in the file or in an associated file in the same folder, such as:

- an **abbreviation list** and/ or a **legend** for documents containing many abbreviations/ acronyms
- an **introduction/ summary** or other additional texts, to better explain the presented data (e.g. objective of data collection, data origin, procedure used for data collection and elaboration)
- **instructions/ guidelines** e.g. for files that have to be completed/ elaborated/ commented by other researchers
- a **readme file** e.g. to clarify the relation among datasets, such as the process of data analysis leading from the raw data to the result data

3.4.2 LICENSES

The licences needed to access the UNITE.H2020 data will be evaluated over the course of the project on a case-by-case evaluation (preferably CC-BY and CC0 licence).

3.4.3 DATA USE BY THIRD PARTIES

In accordance with the GA, it will be possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user, the data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications and all the dataset that will be identified over the course of the project by the consortium and made available with variable timing/ embargo/ restriction and for a length of time on a case by case evaluation.

3.4.4 DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCESS

Each partner is responsible to ensure data quality during data collection, generation, data entry or digitalisation and data checking. Data quality control may include for example:

- clear naming and organization of the project data in folders
- creation of accompanying notes and documentation about the data/ instructions / guidelines about the data

- checking data completeness
- periodic check of the data management procedures by all the partners and proposal/ discussion of possible corrective actions

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 Costs for making data FAIR

All the partners with the supervision of the coordinator will collaborate to make the project data FAIR. In order to manage data and make them FAIR, a relevant effort will be required to the whole project consortium. The cost of such activity is strictly connected to the cost of personnel working time. Moreover, other costs are present, such as partner's costs for data access, storage, security and backup at their local storage system. Other possible costs will be evaluated in the future (e.g. specific software).

4.2 Costs and potential value of long term preservation

In accordance with GA, all the beneficiaries must keep adequate records and documentation related to the project implementation for a period of five years after the payment and until the end of any on-going checks, reviews, audits, investigations, litigation or other pursuits of claims under the Agreement. Each beneficiary should keep a backup of their produced data, documentation, drafts at their own facilities for this required time period. Moreover, WP leaders are encouraged to keep also a backup of all the data of the WP activities on their internal institutional storage systems for the same time period. The data long-term preservation policy and related costs will be discussed among the partners and better defined during the project. Free of charge long term preservation will be ensured for all the data stored on Zenodo repository.

5 Data security

5.1 Data recovery

Each beneficiary should ensure adequate backup and data recovery system for its own research data stored at their local storage systems.

Data recover on uShare repository can be done through the ATIC service at UPCnet, which developed the uShare repository for the Unite! Alliance. Default backup policy establishes daily copies are done with a 28 days retention period (availability). Also, aimed to guarantee system continuity in case of disaster, a full backup with 1 year retention period is made every trimester.

Data recovery on Microsoft Team can be done through the SharePoint.

5.2 Secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

The partner collecting the personal and sensitive data will be responsible for their collection and management in accordance with the EU GDPR. Data containing sensitive personal data will be stored by the responsible partner together with the privacy consent forms in secure password protected environments according to the EU GDPR. Further details can be found in Section 6 Ethical aspects.

5.3 Long-term Archiving and Preservation

As required by the GA, each beneficiary should ensure the archiving and preservation of the data for a period of five years after the payment and until the end of any on-going checks, reviews, audits, investigations, litigation or the pursuits of claims under the Agreement.

The possibility and the modality of data storage for a longer time period will be discussed and evaluated among the partners.

Long term preservation will be ensured for all the data stored on Zenodo repository (e.g. open data).

6 Ethical aspects

As reported in the GA (Section 5: Ethics and Security), as well as in the Ethics Summary Report of EC, in UNITE.H2020 the ethical issues are related to the collection of personal data and their treatment. Each partner has indicated in CA its own Data Controller and Data Protection Officer.

Personal data will be collected, processed and stored during the project. They will be personal data of the staff directly involved in the project and of external people (e.g. from interview, surveys).

Personal data of each beneficiary's **staff involved in the UNITE.H2020 project** will be mainly collected and processed for administrative/ management purposes. The use of them for communication/ dissemination activities could be also considered, after explicit consent of the involved people.

Personal data of **people not directly involved in the project** will be also collected in some interviews/ surveys to personnel belonging to the partner's universities or other universities, industries, stakeholders

and other potential actors of the UNITE.H2020 project, such as civil society (e.g. with survey tools, such as LimeSurvey). The personal data from these interviews/ surveys (e.g. video and/or audio recording, questionnaires etc.) will be collected/ processed/ analysed/ stored for the project activity implementation in compliance with the GDPR and specific procedures will be adopted to ensure data protection/ confidentiality/ privacy.

In accordance with the CA, each beneficiary act as independent Data Controllers to process the personal data related to the project, thus being responsible for their collection for their subsequent management in compliance with EU GDPR. In accordance with the GA, the beneficiaries may grant their personnel access only to data that is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the Agreement.

As regard the **personal data collection**, only **voluntary people over 18** will be interviewed, with possibility of withdrawing at any time the not aggregated/ anonymous data. Each partner in charge of the activity (e.g. survey) is responsible to inform people about the project and for the collection of the **privacy consent form** from the participants for the participation and data use (e.g. publication and sharing). The partners carrying out the activity will ensure that participant consent covers data preservation including the length of time the data will be held, data sharing in the future, the potential for researchers undertaking other projects to access these data and the possibility that this dataset may be available as part of an open access publication or an open access dataset.

As regards **privacy** and **data protection**, data will be anonymized, wherever possible. If it will be not possible, stringent measures in relation to data protection will be used, such as security of records, encryption, coding, use of pseudonyms and removal of identifying contextual information.

As regards **storing of personal data**, all data will be kept in secure password protected environments (e.g. access controlled areas), will be made anonymous if needed and used solely for the purposes of the project. Where data will be collected in electronic format (through on-line questionnaires), the partner responsible for that activity will ensure that precautions will be made to ensure confidentiality, anonymity, privacy and security. Also the consent forms will be stored in a data repository.

7 Responsibility

This Data Management Plan aims to provide common guidelines as suggestion for the UNITE.H2020 consortium for the management of the project data. All the partners with the supervision of the coordinator collaborate to implement the DMP and to make project data FAIR.

In accordance with the GA, the project coordinator is responsible for the delivery and update of the Data Management Plan and for the management of UNITE.H2020 data (collected, processed and/or generated in the project) following the FAIR principles. The project coordinator will act being firstly

responsible for protecting and managing project data and outputs in terms of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).

Each partner is responsible for ensuring proper management and processing of all data collected during the project, complying with the EU DGPR.

